

TITLE:FREQUENCY OF AIDS IN PEOPLE OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Anatasia. Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome is a human disease caused by a virus belonging to the retrovirus group

Ways of transmission, classification, degrees and stages of transmission, the frequency of transmission at different ages. Therefore, AIDS is mainly transmitted in three ways: through blood, through sexual intercourse, and vertically from an infected mother to her fetus.

Key words. AIDS, retrovirus, Peripheral neuropathy, Guillain-Barre syndrome CD4+ T-cells, HIV infection

Acquired immune deficiency syndrome is a disease caused by a virus belonging to the retrovirus group in humans. Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) is a disease caused by a virus belonging to the retrovirus group; divided into two periods: HIV infection and immediate AIDS (SPID) period. The period of HIV infection is the period when the human body has the virus, but the symptoms of the disease have not yet appeared. The virus was discovered almost simultaneously by scientists led by Professor Luc Montagnier in Paris and Professor Gallo in the United States (1983). This virus selectively affects the human immune system, specifically killing CD4+ immune cells. After the virus enters the human body, 2-3 days later, in 25-30% of cases, symptoms characteristic of the period of primary infection can be observed. This is called "acute seroconversion syndrome" and can cause fever, night sweats, joint and headache pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and a rash on the body, especially on the upper body. These symptoms are related to the response of the immune system to a certain extent to the effect of the virus on the human body. But detection of antibodies during this period does not give results, because the response of the immune system is not yet fully formed. This period of the disease can last up to 8-10 years, sometimes even longer. Currently, the diagnosis of HIV infection in practice is based on the detection of antibodies against the disease virus in the blood - enzyme immunoassay (EIA) reaction. Although the initial antibodies begin to form after 3 weeks after the virus enters the body, the used diagnostics cannot detect them. Therefore, it is possible to

conclude that a person is infected with this infection based on the result of the examination conducted 90 days after the virus enters the body. The red ribbon is a symbol of solidarity with people infected with HIV and AIDS. AIDS is the final stage of HIV infection. The fight between the virus and the organism continues for a long time and ends with the virus's victory.

From this time the era of AIDS begins. During this period, the human body loses its resistance to any microbes. In particular, germs that are always present in the respiratory, gastrointestinal, and urinary tracts and cannot cause disease can become active and cause various diseases. Since their manifestation is related to the AIDS situation in the body, diseases belonging to this group are collectively called AIDS-related (associated) infections. These are bacterial infections, fungal diseases, viral diseases, Kaposi's sarcoma, etc. The virus is found in the blood of an infected person, in the semen of men, in the secretions of the genital organs of women, and in breast milk. Therefore, AIDS is mainly transmitted in three ways: through blood, through sexual intercourse, and vertically from an infected mother to her fetus. The majority of people with AIDS are drug addicts, prostitutes, homosexuals and bisexuals. AIDS is transmitted to the body during sexual intercourse, parenteral procedures (when non-sterile needles, syringes and other medical equipment are used), use of infected blood and its substitutes, organ and tissue transplantation (transplantation), as well as during pregnancy, during childbirth from an infected mother to the fetus. and if the baby is breastfed, it can be transmitted through breast milk. Issues related to HIV/AIDS in Uzbekistan are handled by the HIV/AIDS service of the Ministry of Health. The Republican HIV/AIDS Center, the HIV/AIDS Center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the HIV/AIDS Centers of Tashkent city and regions conduct all preventive, epidemiological, laboratory examination and treatment measures related to the activities of this field in their territories. Each center has anonymous rooms where people who come for laboratory tests can be tested confidentially. Targeted groups also operate Trust Points (IPs), which work confidentially with drug addicts and sex workers to prevent the spread of the virus. There are three main stages of HIV infection: acute infection, clinical latency, and AIDS. Acute infection The first period after HIV infection is called acute HIV, primary HIV, or acute retroviral syndrome. Many people develop an illness like the flu, mononucleosis, or glandular fever 2-4 weeks after exposure, while others have no noticeable symptoms. Symptoms occur in 40–90% of cases and most commonly include fever, enlarged lymph nodes, sore throat, rash,

headache, fatigue, and/or oral and genital ulcers. The rash, which occurs in 20–50% of cases, presents on the trunk and is classically maculopapular. Since this infection is one of the most common diseases, protection measures should be carried out with the participation of representatives of all spheres of social life. Every young man and woman should be aware of the ways of spreading this infection, measures to prevent it and protect themselves from it.

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